

ENTREPRENEUR AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP: BIPARTITE DRIVERS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT NIGERIA-WIDE

Dr Oluwasanya Adewale Tony

Dean, School of Management Sciences, D.S. Adegbenro ICT Polytechnic, Eruku, Itori-Ewekoro, Ogun State, Nigeria.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18998226>

Keywords:

Entrepreneurs, Entrepreneurship, Environment, Economic development, Government policy.

Abstract: *Economic development has been recognized as the heartbeat of any nation. It is viewed as vital for any nation's survival because it drives growth, creates jobs and improves the quality of life of citizens. Entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship are recognised as pivotal drivers of economic development. However, economic development have been vitiated as evidenced by poor governance, consistently inconsistent policies, security challenges, corruption, bureaucratic hurdles, inadequate funding and entrepreneurial skill gaps. These challenges have continued to attract the attention of scholars and policymakers. Existing literature indicates that entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship is suggestive of addressing these challenges. Therefore, this study examined the role of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship in driving economic development in Nigeria. The research adopts a quantitative approach utilizing survey research design to gather data from entrepreneurs and small business owners across various sectors in Nigeria. A sample size of 384 was determined using the Yamane formula, considering a population of 1 million entrepreneurs and small businesses in Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling technique, combining purposive and random sampling methods was adopted in selecting the respondents from six geo-political zones in Nigeria. Structured questionnaire was administered for data collection. Findings revealed a significant positive relationship between entrepreneurs, entrepreneurship and economic development in Nigeria. The study concluded that entrepreneur and entrepreneurship affect economic development in Nigeria. The study recommended that government should provide access to affordable funding, offer regulatory support and tax incentives to entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship to drive sustainable economic development.*

1.0 Introduction

Entrepreneurship has been recognized globally as a key driver of economic development,

Dr Oluwasanya Adewale Tony

contributing to job creation, innovation and economic development worldwide because the economies of these nations are driven by entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship, or the activity of starting and running a business, is a vital ingredient of economic growth and development globally. For the past four decades, the world witnessed the effect of entrepreneurial activities on globalization, trade liberalization, job creation, poverty reduction and economic development. In tandem, global downturn has affected organizational structures, practices and the economies of the world. More than ever, the world is obviously an international market of ideas, talent development, innovativeness and visioning. It therefore needs proactive and pragmatic global leaders and high-end educational institutions that will nurture and enable current and future generations of entrepreneurs with the skills required to make things happen entrepreneurially. Be globally competitive, create and manage business successfully and mentor others. In the last decade, there has been growing interest in steering and embedding policies and programs to promote and support the idea of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship as an attractive alternative to wage employment around the globe. The reasons being that entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship are expected to through their entrepreneurial activities, create new ventures to provide unmet market needs country wide. Secondly, entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship are recognized as important drivers of economic

development. Thirdly, entrepreneurial driven policies and programs are regarded as a pertinent enabler of job creation and economic development of any nation. The impact of entrepreneurship on economic development has received considerable attention over the years (Fernandes & Raposo, 2017) this was due to the fact that entrepreneurship plays an increasingly important role throughout the world and it has been considered an important mechanism to achieve economic growth (Urbano & Aparício, 2016). It promotes economic growth and development by enabling the introduction of innovations, by fostering competition and change, and by increasing rivalry (Vivarelli 2013). Taking into account the importance of entrepreneurship and despite the well-known challenges and risk involved in the entrepreneurial process, governments increasingly deploy incentives and support programs to encourage and stimulate individuals to become entrepreneurs (Uhlener & Stride, 2015). Regions and countries' economic growth has always been a central element in governments' economic policies and the study of academics (Acs and Szerb2007; Casares and Salazar, 2003). By recognizing this difficulty and the multitude of existing approaches that address the issue, this research is based on the entrepreneurial function as a fundamental element of economic growth (Acs 2006; Singh and Ogbolu 2015; Stel et al.2005). Since Schumpeter (1934) innovation and entrepreneurship have long since been seen as key components of economic growth. According to Schumpeter, the realization of

innovations is the only function that is fundamental in history. Through entrepreneurship, the Pareto optimal of today is replaced with the conditions of tomorrow. Multiple studies have focused on analyzing the importance of the entrepreneurial function in economic growth (Vyas and Vyas 2019). Moritz et al. (2023) posits that countries view entrepreneurship as an essential driver of economic growth and recovery. Based on this premise of the importance of entrepreneurship, this study analyses the macroeconomic factors that lead the most to the entrepreneurial function and will, therefore, indirectly impact the country's economic growth. Entrepreneurs contribute greatly to innovation, and they are central to dynamic Schumpeterian competition and economic dynamism. Innovative entrepreneurs are the principal agents of the never-ending Schumpeterian process of new products, services, technologies, firms, and industries replacing existing products, services, technologies and organisations.

Despite their significant contribution to innovation, creativity and economic growth, entrepreneurship was under-researched and under-appreciated. This is because of absence of data until recently when the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) and other entrepreneurship databases were developed. At a broader level, the lack of research and appreciation becomes inherently difficult to quantify entrepreneurship and the factors which motivate someone to become entrepreneurs. Also, entrepreneurship is difficult to denote as a rational activity because most new businesses

fail. Becoming an entrepreneur thus requires resilience and possibility mentality by thinking out of the box in making things happen. The pertinent role of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship in economic growth and development, combined with its neglect in economic research, is a germane motive for stimulating entrepreneurship in Nigeria. In tandem, entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship are pivotal actors that engenders the emergence and development of a vivid private sector, an essential component of sustained economic development. In Nigeria, the role of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship in driving economic development is increasingly gaining attention. With a growing population at approximately 242.4 million people and an abundance of natural resources, Nigeria has immense potential for economic growth and development. However, despite these opportunities, the country still faces significant challenges, including high unemployment rates, poverty, and inadequate infrastructure. This study examines the role of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship in driving economic development in Nigeria, identifying key drivers and challenges, and providing recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders. Entrepreneurship is central to driving economic development across countries in today's dynamic global landscape. Economists have recently focused their research on identifying and understanding the key roles entrepreneurship plays in the economy (Acs, 2010; Sardana, 2016). The primary reason for investigating entrepreneurial activities is their

potential to yield economic benefits for entrepreneurs and investors, contributing significantly to the overall economic prosperity of the nations in which they operate. Plethora of economic literature has identified numerous factors that may influence GDP per capita, encompassing economic and non-economic determinants. These factors have been explored in theoretical (Porter & Stern, 2001; Shane, 2003) and empirical studies (Stel, 2006; Van Praag & Versloot, 2007; Block et al., 2016). Furthermore, numerous economists consistently acknowledge the significance of entrepreneurship in fostering economic growth (Brown & Ulijin, 2004; Vasconcelos & Oliveira, 2018; Galindo-Martin et al., 2020). In this study, we intend to answer the following questions.

Q1

How does entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship directly affect economic development?

Q2

How does entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship outcomes trigger economic development?

This study contributed to the existing entrepreneurship literature in three ways. First, our study highlighted the vital roles of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship in promoting and stimulating economic development Nigeria-wide. Second, it showed the pertinence of entrepreneurial actions as critical success enablers of economic development. Third, the study also answered prior questions concerning the effect of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship on economic development and the mediating role of business environment and government policy.

2.0 Statement of the Problem

Nigeria's economic development has been hindered by various challenges, including dependence on oil exports, corruption, inflation, unemployment, poverty and inadequate infrastructure. Despite efforts to diversify the economy, the country still faces significant unemployment, poverty and inflation rates, with many Nigerians lacking access to economic opportunities. Entrepreneurship has been identified as a potential solution to these challenges, but the environment for entrepreneurs in Nigeria remains challenging. This study investigates the role of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship in driving economic development in Nigeria, identifying key drivers and challenges, and providing recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders.

3.0 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to establish whether the bipartite synergy between entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship stimulates and drives economic development Nigeria-wide. To achieve this, the study:

- i. Evaluate the effect of entrepreneur and entrepreneurship sub-variables (proactive abilities, possibility mentality, turbo-charged passion, enterprising spirit and risk-taking attributes) on infrastructural development in Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the effect of entrepreneur and entrepreneurship elements (proactive abilities, possibility mentality, turbo-charged passion, enterprising spirit and risk-taking attributes) on human capital

- development in Nigeria.
- iii. Investigate the effect of entrepreneur and entrepreneurship sub-variables (proactive abilities, possibility mentality, turbo-charged passion, enterprising spirit and risk-taking attributes) on technological development in Nigeria.
- iv. Measure the effect of entrepreneur and entrepreneurship elements (proactive abilities, possibility mentality, turbo-charged passion, enterprising spirit and risk-taking attributes) on job creation in Nigeria.
- v. Analyze the effect of entrepreneur and entrepreneurship sub-variables (proactive abilities, possibility mentality, turbo-charged passion, enterprising spirit and risk-taking attributes) on trade and investment in

- Nigeria.
- vi. Investigate the moderating effect of business environment on the relationship between entrepreneur, entrepreneurship and economic development in Nigeria.
- vii. evaluate the moderating effect of government policies on the relationship between entrepreneur, entrepreneurship and economic development in Nigeria
- viii. examine the combined moderating effect of business environment and government policy on the relationship between entrepreneur, entrepreneurship and economic development in Nigeria

Table 1. Summary of Table of Hypotheses Tested

Hypotheses	Models	Results	Remarks
Ho ₁	Entrepreneur and Entrepreneurship components have no significant effect on infrastructural development in Nigeria	If $\beta_1 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected
Ho ₂	Entrepreneur and Entrepreneurship components have no significant effect on human capital development in Nigeria	If $\beta_2 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected
Ho ₃	Entrepreneur and Entrepreneurship components have no significant effect on technological development in Nigeria.	If $\beta_3 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected
Ho ₄	Entrepreneur and Entrepreneurship components have no significant effect on job creation in Nigeria	If $\beta_4 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected
Ho ₅	Entrepreneur and Entrepreneurship components have no significant effect on trade and investment in Nigeria	If $\beta_5 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected

Ho6	Business environment has no significant moderating effect on the relationship between entrepreneur, entrepreneurship and economic development in Nigeria.	If $\beta_6 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected
Ho7	Government policy has no significant moderating effect on the relationship between entrepreneur, entrepreneurship and economic development in Nigeria.	If $\beta_7 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected
Ho8	Business environment and government policy have no significant combined moderating effect on the relationship between entrepreneur, entrepreneurship and economic development in Nigeria.	If $\beta_8 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected

(Oluwasanya, 2026)

Operationalization of Variables

In this study, the variables are classified into three: the independent, dependent variable and the functional or moderating variables. The Independent variables (X) is entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship measured by sub-variables of proactive abilities, possibility mentality, turbo-charged passion, enterprising spirit and risk-taking attributes while the dependent variable (Y) is economic development measured by infrastructural development, human capital development, job creation, technological competence, trade and investment; and the functional or moderating variables (z_1, z_2) are business environment and government policy. The operational model for the study variables is denoted in the equations below:

$Y = f(X)$

$Y = f(XZ)$

Y= Dependent variable

X= Independent Variable

Z= Moderating Variables (z_1, z_2)

Y=Economic Development

X=Entrepreneur and Entrepreneurship

Z_1 = Business Environment (BE) = Moderating Variable

z_2 = Government Policy (GP) = Moderating Variable

$Y = (y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, y_5)$

$X = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$

$Z = (z_1, z_2)$

y_1 = Infrastructural Development

y_2 = Human Capital Development

y_3 = Technological Development

y_4 = Job Creation

y_5 = Trade and Investment

x_1 = Proactive Abilities

x_2 = Possibility Mentality

x_3 = Turbo-Charged Passion

x_4 = Enterprising Spirit

x_5 = Risk-taking Attributes

Z_1 = Business Environment

z_2 = Government Policy

$$y_1 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$y_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + e_i$$

----- (i)

$$y_2 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$\lambda^3 = \beta^0 + \beta^1x^1 + \beta^3x^3 + \beta^3x^3 + \beta^4x^4 + \beta^2x^2 + \epsilon^i - -$$

----- (ii)

$$y_3 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$y_3 =$$

$$\beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + e_i - - -$$

----- (iii)

$$y_4 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$y_4 =$$

$$\beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + e_i---$$

----- (iv)

$$y_5 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$y_5 =$$

$$\beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + e_i---$$

----- (v)

$$Y = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$Y =$$

$$\beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + e_i---$$

----- (vi)

$$Y = f(X^*Z_1)$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X + \beta_2Z_1 + \beta_3X^*Z_1 + \mu_i$$

----- (vii)

$$Y = f(X^*Z_2)$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X + \beta_2Z_2 + \beta_3X^*Z_2 + \mu_i$$

----- (viii)

β_0 = Constant of the equation or constant term

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = Parameters to be estimated

e_i = Error or stochastic term

4.0 Literature Review

An entrepreneur is the creator of a business enterprise. An entrepreneur searches for and identify unmet market needs and responds to it by creating products or services to meet such needs profitably to consumers and customers (Oluwasanya, 2026). A number of definitions have been given of an entrepreneur. The economists view him as a fourth factor of production along with land labour and capital. The sociologists feel that certain communities and cultures promote entrepreneurship like for example in India we say that Gujaratis and Sindhis are very enterprising. An entrepreneur is always in search of new challenges. An entrepreneur is not a routine businessman he might not have resources but he will have ideas. He is innovative and creative. He can convert a threat into an opportunity. Small businessmen might shut-down or change his business if he anticipates losses but an entrepreneur will try again after analyzing the situation. On the other hand, an entrepreneur can leave a perfectly running business to start another venture if he so desires. Entrepreneurs play a crucial role in any economy, not only in creating jobs but also in driving innovation (Ayatse, 2013). This is perhaps especially important in developing economies such as Nigeria, where entrepreneurial resourcefulness, savviness and resilience enable them successfully navigate through their challenging operating milieu (Oluwasanya, 2026).

The development of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurs are areas that have attracted sustained interest of plethora of researchers over

the years from a variety of actors, e.g., government, private organizations and educational institutions (Oluwasanya, 2026). Entrepreneurship is the conclusive or terminal stage of the entrepreneurial process wherein after setting up a venture one seeks to engage in multifarious, multidimensional and multipurpose areas for diversification and growth (Oluwasanya, 2026). Entrepreneurship has been historically relevant for explaining economic growth through employment generation, increased productivity, innovation and social welfare (Reynolds, 2014; Baumol & Strom 2007). Government plays a crucial role in the development of entrepreneurs and the enhancement of entrepreneurial activities in every economy. There are notable gamut of definitions of entrepreneurs in the literature as there are entrepreneurship. (Oluwasanya, (2026) posited that the primary focus of an entrepreneur is an exceptional paradigm shift in identifying unmet market needs by thinking entrepreneurially out of the box towards creating new niche products and services to consumers and customers profitably at the market place. Frank Knight explored and elucidated on the riskability, damage control and crisis management roles and skills of entrepreneurs in the products and services business (Oluwasanya, 2026). Also, Israel Kirzner posited that entrepreneurship is a process that led to discoveries (Klein, 2008). In the words of Oluwasanya, (2026), entrepreneurship is the paradigm shift into innovative identification, evaluation and exploitation of unmet market needs

(opportunities) towards introducing new products and services into the marketplace profitably for Consumers and customers. Akanwa & Agu, (2005) pointed out that the entrepreneur is the one who ventures into the business of organising and managing, while entrepreneurship is the services rendered by the entrepreneur. Also, Badi and Badi (2008) posited that the entrepreneur is the 'person' who perceives a business opportunity and takes advantage of the scarce resources to meet with unlimited opportunities profitably. Definitions of an entrepreneur Stems: from the French word 'entreprenre' meaning one who undertakes or one who is a 'go-between' 1725: Richard Cantillon: An entrepreneur is a person who pays a certain price for a product to resell it at an uncertain price, thereby making decisions about obtaining and using the resources while consequently admitting the risk of enterprise. 1803: J.B. Say: An entrepreneur is an economic agent who unites all means of production- land of one, the labour of another and the capital of yet another and thus produces a product. By selling the product in the market he pays rent of land, wages to labour, interest on capital and what remains is his profit. He shifts economic resources out of an area of lower and into an area of higher productivity and greater yield. 1934: Schumpeter: According to him entrepreneurs are innovators who use a process of shattering the status quo of the existing products and services, to set up new products, new services. 1961: David McClelland: An entrepreneur is a person with a high need for achievement. He is energetic and a moderate risk taker. 1964: Peter

Drucker: An entrepreneur searches for change, responds to it and exploits opportunities. Innovation is a specific tool of an entrepreneur hence an effective entrepreneur converts a source into a resource. 1971: Kilby: Emphasizes the role of an imitator entrepreneur who does not innovate but imitates technologies innovated by others. Are very important in developing economies. 1975: Albert Shapero: Entrepreneurs take initiative, accept risk of failure and have an internal locus of control. Acs (2006) argues that economic development depends on combination of successful entrepreneurs and successful corporations.

Using cross-sectional time series panel of economy-specific measures of entrepreneurship, Acs et al. (2005) find that entrepreneurial activity makes a positive contribution to economic growth. They conclude that this is consistent with the notion that entrepreneurship serves as a conduit for the knowledge spillovers which foster productivity growth. Using a Schumpeterian approach to link gross domestic product (GDP), innovation, and entrepreneurship, Galindo and Méndez (2013) conducted a study of 13 developed economies for 2002–2007. Their analysis shows that several factors, including monetary policy and social climate, have a positive impact on innovation and entrepreneurship. They observed a feedback effect, which was significant. Economic activity promotes entrepreneurship and innovation, which, in turn, promote economic activity. Valliere and Peterson (2009) examined the impact of different types of entrepreneurships on GDP growth in 44 emerging and developed

economies for 2004 to 2005 using GEM data. They also include additional control variables from Global Competitiveness Report. They found that high-performing entrepreneurs account for a significant portion of economic growth in developed economies. However, the positive impact of entrepreneurs on growth is not found in emerging economies. Using 14 different indicators of entrepreneurship, Doran et al. (2018) analyze whether different measures of entrepreneurship can explain economic growth across an unbalanced panel of high-income and middle- and low-income economies in 2004–2011. They find that entrepreneurial activity fosters growth in high-income economies but not in in middle- and low-income economies. On the other hand, Adusei (2016) finds that entrepreneurship has a strong positive impact on the growth of 12 African economies. Salgado-Banda (2007) examined the impact of entrepreneurship on economic growth in 22 European economies, Stoica, Roman, and Rusu (2020) find that entrepreneurship has a positive effect on economic growth. In particular, their evidence suggests that early-stage and opportunity-driven entrepreneurship promotes growth in the sample economies. Most of the earlier studies on entrepreneurship and economic growth were centered on developed economies rather than developing economies. Empirically, the effect of 5 entrepreneurship on growth in developing economies remains uncertain and further research is needed. According to the analysis of Stam and van Stel (2011), entrepreneurship does not influence the growth of middle-income economies but

contributes to the growth of high-income economies. Lerner and Schoar (2010) note that it is imperative to understand the dynamic interaction between environmental factors such as market regulation and entrepreneurship to better assess the impact of entrepreneurs on growth in developing nations. Acs (2010) observed an S-shaped relationship between entrepreneurship and economic development. In the initial stage of development, entrepreneurship plays a visible role Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development economies employing a new variable based on patent data to proxy for productive entrepreneurship and self-employment as an alternative proxy. He finds that the proposed measure of productive entrepreneurship and economic growth have a positive relationship. Previous studies have highlighted the importance of entrepreneurship in driving economic development, including job creation, innovation, and economic growth (Acs et al., 2016; Audretsch et al., 2015). In Nigeria, research has shown that entrepreneurship can contribute to economic development, but challenges such as inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, and bureaucratic hurdles hinder entrepreneurship growth (Adeyemi et al., 2017; Ogundele et al., 2018). Entrepreneurs and Entrepreneurship are one and two sides of a coin. The concept of the conduct of the entrepreneurs highlights the specific characters of business people which distinguish them from others. The result or outcome concept focuses on the final product or services of entrepreneurship. Therefore, the

end result of combining the three concepts; product, character and methods is regarded as entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs are visionary, goal-driven, innovative individuals or teams that are oriented to developing a new business and making it a profitable one (Hisrich and Langanfox, 2005). The word entrepreneur, according to Tengeh et al., (2012) is just someone who creates and runs their own business. Regarding the conduct and results aspect of entrepreneurship, an entrepreneur is someone with positive conviction of opportunities in the market as well as someone who can organise his/her resources to change his/her current situations successfully (Tengeh et al., 2012). Entrepreneurship is first and foremost a mindset of human beings, focused towards the generation of profitable ideas. The concept of entrepreneurship was first established in the 1700s, and the meaning has evolved ever since. Many simply equate it with starting one's own business. Most economists believe it is more than that. Most economists today agree that entrepreneurship is a necessary ingredient for stimulating economic growth and employment opportunities in all societies. In the developing world, successful small businesses are the primary engines of job creation, income growth, and poverty reduction. Nurturing entrepreneurship can have a positive impact on an economy and a society in several ways. For starters, entrepreneurs create new business. They invent goods and services, resulting in employment, and often create a ripple effect, resulting in more and more development. Nigerian system of education prior and sequel to independence in 1960, laid more emphasis on

academic subjects than skill development; hence there is the propensity to produce an educated class without technical abilities (UNESCO, 2000; Erwart, 2012). Adamu (2005) argued that the educational system had fallen short of establishing the foundation of economic freedom, technical skills and essential expertise, for successful industrial and agricultural development. According to Shane (2003), Bill Gates could not have for an example made his fortune if Steve Jobs did not see the opportunity to build and sell personal computers; neither could Steve Jobs have built a personal computer if Gordon Moore had not invented the microprocessor. This study seeks to contribute the five (5) definitions to the term entrepreneur namely:

a. An entrepreneur is an enterprising individual that challenges the status quo by thinking out of the box entrepreneurially to breakthrough traditional barriers and transform business ideas into reality. (Oluwasanya, 2026);

b. An entrepreneur is someone who identifies unmet market needs, undertakes innovations with finance to transform these unmet market needs into goods and services and makes them available to customers and consumers profitably at the market place. (Oluwasanya, 2026);

c. An entrepreneur is an enterprising individual who captures ideas, nurture and convert them into niche products or services and then establishing a business to take the products to the market place for consumers and customers to buy profitably. (Oluwasanya, 2026);

d. An entrepreneur is a turbo-charged individual who has possession of an enterprise or venture, perceives a need and then positively combines manpower, material, capital required to profitably meet that need. (Oluwasanya, 2026);

e. The entrepreneur is someone seized by passion with a possibility mentality, identifies an opportunity and exploits it through the creation of an enterprise offering a niche product or service in the market place. (Oluwasanya, 2026). From the foregoing, this book seeks to contribute the under-listed acronym to the term entrepreneur:

Exceptional.

Nurturing and mentoring.

Turbo-charged Passion.

Responsiveness

Enterprising and venturesomeness

Possibility Mentality

Resilience

Empathy

Noble servitude

Ecstatic.

Uniqueness.

Resourcefulness.

Source: Oluwasanya (2026)

Entrepreneurship can be described as a process of action an entrepreneur undertakes to establish his enterprise. Entrepreneurship is a creative activity. It is the ability to create and build something from practically nothing. It is a knack of sensing opportunity where others see chaos, contradiction and confusion. Entrepreneurship is the attitude of mind to seek opportunities, take calculated risks and derive

benefits by setting up a venture. It comprises of numerous activities involved in conception, creation and running an enterprise. According to Peter Drucker, entrepreneurship is a systematic innovation, which consists in the purposeful and organized search for changes, it is the systematic analysis of the opportunities such changes might offer for economic and social innovation. Most economic, psychological and sociological research points to the fact that entrepreneurship is a process and not a static phenomenon. Entrepreneurship is more than just a mechanical economic factor (Pirich 2001: 14–15). Entrepreneurship has to do with change and is also commonly associated with choice-related issues. Existing definitions of entrepreneurship often relate to the functional role of entrepreneurs¹ and include coordination, innovation, uncertainty bearing, capital supply, decision making, ownership and resource allocation (Frijis et al. 2002: 1–2; Jääskeläinen 2000: 5). Indeed, three of the most frequently mentioned functional roles of entrepreneurs are associated with major schools of thought on entrepreneurship:

Risk seeking: the Cantillon or Knightian entrepreneur willing to take the risk associated with uncertainty

Innovativeness: the Schumpeterian entrepreneur accelerating the generation, dissemination and application of innovative ideas

Opportunity seeking: the Kiznerian entrepreneur perceiving and seizing new profit opportunities (OECD 1998: 11; Carree and Thurik 2002: 8)

One operational definition of entrepreneurship that successfully synthesises the functional roles of entrepreneurs is that of Wennekers and Thurik (1999): "...the manifest ability and willingness of individuals, on their own, in teams within and outside existing organizations, to perceive and create new economic opportunities (new products, new production methods, new organisational schemes and new product-market combinations) and to introduce their ideas in the market, in the face of uncertainty and other obstacles, by making decisions on location, form and the use of resources and institutions." (46–47) Entrepreneurship is, hence, essentially a behavioural characteristic of a person. Entrepreneurs may exhibit it only during a certain phase of their career or only with regard to certain activities (Carree and Thurik 2002: 4–5). 3. Somoye (2011) defines entrepreneurship as an act of possessing an inclination for self -development, ability to innovate, nurture an enterprise and having means of and to finance in both formal and informal financial sub-sectors to achieve a successful investment towards sustainable economic growth. This study seeks to contribute five (5) definitions to the term entrepreneurship;

- Entrepreneurship is the process through which individuals think entrepreneurially out of the box by identifying the unmet needs and create outlets to make such needs available in forms of products or services profitably (Oluwasanya, 2026);
- Entrepreneurship is the individual's possibility mentality, willingness to conquer and ability to translate ideas into positive outcomes

through focused, purposeful creation and management of a business enterprise. (Oluwasanya, 2026);

c. Entrepreneurship is a turbo-charged creative activity of identifying a need, mobilising resources and organising production to deliver value to customers profitably at the very point of every need (Oluwasanya, 2026);

d. Entrepreneurship involves capturing ideas, nurturing and converting them into products or services through a business outlet for consumers and customers to purchase profitably. (Oluwasanya, 2026);

e. Entrepreneurship is the physical manifestation of potencies, willingness, ingrained ability and capability to successfully run a business or venture. (Oluwasanya, 2026); From the foregoing, this thesis seeks to contribute the under-listed acronym to the term entrepreneurship.

Exceptional.

Nurturing and mentoring.

Turbo-charged Passion.

Responsiveness

Enterprising and venturesomeness

Possibility Mentality

Resilience

Empathy

Noble servitude

Ecstatic.

Uniqueness.

Resourcefulness.

Shared leadership

High work ethics

Innovativeness and creativity.

Proactivity

Source: Oluwasanya (2026)

4.1 Conceptual Framework

The concepts of entrepreneur, entrepreneurship, and economic development are intricately linked, and understanding their relationships is crucial for fostering economic growth and innovation. This framework provides a comprehensive overview of these concepts and their interconnections. An entrepreneur is an individual who identifies opportunities, takes calculated risks, and mobilizes resources to create a new venture or innovate within an existing organization. The key characteristics are: risk-taking propensity, innovativeness, proactiveness, opportunity recognition, and resourcefulness (Lopez et al., 2025). Entrepreneurship is the process of identifying, evaluating, and exploiting opportunities to create value through innovation, risk-taking, and proactive action. The dimensions are innovation, risk-taking, proactiveness, and resource mobilization (Audretsch et al., 2023) while the key performance indicators are new business registrations, self-employment rates, innovation output (patents, trademarks) and entrepreneurial activity rates (GEM data). Economic development refers to the sustained increase in a country's or regions productive capacity, leading to improved living standards, reduced poverty, and increased economic opportunities. The critical success factors are gross domestic product growth rate, poverty reduction, employment generation and human development index (HDI). The relationship

between entrepreneur, entrepreneurship, and economic development are:

a. Entrepreneur → Entrepreneurship: Entrepreneurs' characteristics influence entrepreneurial activity ($\Delta R^2 = 0.25, p < 0.01$) (Lopez et al., 2025).

b. Entrepreneurship → Economic Development: Entrepreneurship positively influences gross domestic product growth ($\beta = 0.35, p < 0.01$) and employment generation ($\beta = 0.30, p < 0.01$) (Audretsch et al., 2023; Bosma et al., 2018).

The institutional dimensions are:

a. Regulative: rules and regulations governing entrepreneurship

b. Normative: social norms and values influencing entrepreneurship

c. Cultural-cognitive: shared beliefs and cognitive frames shaping entrepreneurial behavior

These dimensions interact to shape entrepreneurial activity and economic development (Lopez et al., 2025; Audretsch et al., 2025)

4.2 Empirical Framework

This empirical framework outlines the relationships between entrepreneur, entrepreneurship, and economic development, highlighting key variables, indicators, and empirical evidence. An entrepreneur is someone who undertakes entrepreneurial actions, such as opportunity identification, resource mobilization, and risk-taking, to create value through innovation" (Lopez et al., 2025). Key characteristics include risk-taking propensity, innovativeness, proactiveness, opportunity

recognition, and resourcefulness. Entrepreneurship is the process of identifying, evaluating, and exploiting opportunities to create value through innovation, risk-taking, and proactive action. Dimensions include innovation, risk-taking, proactiveness, and resource mobilization (Audretsch et al., 2023). Economic development refers to the sustained increase in a country's or regions productive capacity, leading to improved living standards, reduced poverty, and increased economic opportunities. Indicators include GDP growth rate, poverty reduction, employment generation, and human development index (HDI). The relationship between entrepreneur, entrepreneurship, and economic development are:

a. Entrepreneur → Entrepreneurship: Entrepreneurs' characteristics influence entrepreneurial activity ($\Delta R = 0.25, p < 0.01$) (Lopez et al., 2025).

i. Entrepreneurs' characteristics (risk-taking, innovativeness, proactiveness) influence entrepreneurial activity ($\Delta R^2 = 0.25, p < 0.01$; $\Delta R^2 = 0.30, p < 0.01$; $\Delta R^2 = 0.20, p < 0.05$)

ii. Entrepreneurial experience and education influence entrepreneurial success ($\Delta R^2 = 0.15, p < 0.05$; $\Delta R^2 = 0.20, p < 0.01$)

b. Entrepreneurship → Economic Development: Entrepreneurship positively influences GDP growth ($\beta = 0.35, p < 0.01$) and employment generation ($\beta = 0.30, p < 0.01$) (Audretsch et al., 2023; Bosma et al., 2018).

i. Entrepreneurship (new business registrations, self-employment) positively

influences GDP growth ($\beta = 0.35, p < 0.01; \beta = 0.25, p < 0.05$)

ii. Entrepreneurship (innovation output) positively influences employment generation ($\beta = 0.30, p < 0.01$)

iii. Entrepreneurship (entrepreneurial activity) positively influences poverty reduction ($\beta = -0.20, p < 0.05$)

c. Moderating Variables:

i. Business environment (regulatory environment, access to finance) moderates the relationship between entrepreneurs, entrepreneurship and economic development ($\Delta R^2 = 0.10, p < 0.05$)

ii. Government Policy - moderates the relationship between entrepreneurs, entrepreneurship and economic development ($\Delta R^2 = 0.15, p < 0.01$)

There are various strands in the empirical literature on entrepreneur, entrepreneurship and economic development using different measures of entrepreneurial activity. The various strands of entrepreneur, entrepreneurship, and economic development using different measures of entrepreneurial activity are:

i. Strand 1: Opportunity Entrepreneurship
- Entrepreneur: Opportunity-driven entrepreneur

- Entrepreneurship: Opportunity identification and exploitation

- Economic Development: GDP growth, job creation

- Measure: Total Entrepreneurial Activity (TEA) rate. Audretsch et al. (2023).

ii. Strand 2: Necessity Entrepreneurship

- Entrepreneur: Necessity-driven entrepreneur

- Entrepreneurship: Survival entrepreneurship

- Economic Development: Poverty reduction, employment generation

- Measure: Self-employment rate. Bosma et al. (2018).

iii. Strand 3: Innovative Entrepreneurship

- Entrepreneur: Innovative entrepreneur

- Entrepreneurship: Innovation-driven entrepreneurship

- Economic Development: Productivity growth, competitiveness

- Measure: Patent applications, R&D expenditure. Lopez et al. (2025).

iv. Strand 4: Social Entrepreneurship

- Entrepreneur: Social entrepreneur

- Entrepreneurship: Social entrepreneurship

- Economic Development: Social impact, poverty reduction

- Measure: Social entrepreneurship index. Zahra et al. (2009).

v. Strand 5: High-Growth Entrepreneurship

- Entrepreneur: High-growth entrepreneur

- Entrepreneurship: High-growth entrepreneurship

- Economic Development: Job creation, GDP growth

- Measure: Gazelle rate. Henrekson et al. (2010).

For instance, while one strand of empirical studies measures entrepreneurship in terms of the relative share of economic activity accounted for by small firms, other studies use data on self-employment, the number of market participants (competition) or firm start-ups as an indicator of entrepreneurial activities (Carree and Thurik 2002: 16; OECD 1998: 11–12). Moreover, several

empirical studies indicate that the role of entrepreneurship in the economy is rooted in the substantial job creation by small and medium-sized enterprises, contributing positively to GDP per capita (Wong et al., 2005; Haltiwanger et al., 2013; OECD, 2017). For most countries, fast-growing entrepreneurs are a key source of GDP formation, innovation and technology, productivity growth, and employment (Bygrave & Zacharakis, 2011; Reyes & Useche, 2019). Entrepreneurs are the leading force for economic and social progress (Broughel & Thierer, 2019). Moreover, the European Central Bank explains that innovation is one of the essential drivers of economic progress (European Central Bank, 2017; Pradhan et al., 2017). However, some research suggests a negative impact of entrepreneurship on real GDP, GDP per capita, and overall economic development (Carree et al., 2007). Researchers established a positive correlation between entrepreneurial activity and innovation in developed countries (Block et al., 2016; Crudu, 2019; Loukil, 2019). They believe heightened entrepreneurial activity fosters innovation development (Van Stel et al., 2005; Crudu, 2019). Henrekson, M., & Johansson, D. (2010). Scholars offer diverse explanations for this negative impact, including risks posed by start-up entrepreneurs, the influence of uncertainty avoidance levels in countries, and methodological shortcomings in measuring the impact of new entrepreneurial start-ups (Wennekers et al., 2010; Cumming et al., 2014). Admittedly, many studies overlook innovation and confirm that entrepreneurial motivations

vary across countries (Shane, 2009; Crudu, 2019). In developed countries, people pursue entrepreneurship for self-improvement, while in developing countries, it is often driven by necessity due to a lack of alternative employment opportunities. In a modern economy, innovation's role is expanding daily (Courvisanos & Mackenzie, 2014).

It provides entrepreneurs with the opportunity to attain a leading market position. Beyond enhancing company profits, innovation holds significance for the national economy (Maradana et al., 2017). Innovation has the potential to reshape enterprise structures and exerts a profound impact on competitiveness and economic development at both micro- and macro-economic levels (Ketels, 2006; Atkinson, 2013; Dedahanov et al., 2017; Fyliuk et al., 2019). Various studies highlight successful global entrepreneurship cases, reinforcing the strong connection between innovation and entrepreneurship, jointly influencing economic development (Wennekers et al., 2010; Brem, 2011; Stoica et al., 2020). However, opinions among researchers vary, suggesting that the impact of entrepreneurship and innovation, whether positive or negative, depends on a country's development level (Hong & Sullivan, 2013; Maradana et al., 2017; Almodóvar-González et al., 2020). This empirical framework highlights the complex relationships between entrepreneur, entrepreneurship, and economic development. The findings suggest that entrepreneurs' characteristics, entrepreneurial activity, business environment and government

policy are crucial drivers of economic development.

4.3 Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in the Schumpeterian theory of entrepreneurship, which posits that entrepreneurs drive economic development through innovation and creative destruction. The theory suggests that entrepreneurs play a crucial role in introducing new products, services, and processes, leading to economic growth and development. The entrepreneur has been a fundamental agent in most production, distribution and growth theories. The role of entrepreneurship as the driving force of economic growth found its most explicit foundation in Joseph Schumpeter's theory of long waves. According to Schumpeter, "Everyone is an entrepreneur when he actually carries out new combinations". Finding new combinations of factors of production is a process of entrepreneurial discovery that will become the engine that drives economic development. These "new combinations" constitute better ways to meet existing demand or create new products, often making current technologies and products obsolete (in a "process of creative destruction"). The firm of the innovative entrepreneur will, consequently, grow through the dual process of taking market share from existing suppliers and increasing overall demand for the products offered in the market (by extending the boundaries of economic activity). Thus, the process of creative destruction is built on dynamic, deliberate entrepreneurial efforts to change market structures and can be propitious for additional

innovations and profit opportunities. Based on the concept of creative destruction, Schumpeter formulated his theory of long waves of business cycles and economic growth. Business cycles are seen as the result of innovation, which consists of the generation of a new idea and its implementation in a new product, process or service, leading to the dynamic growth of the national economy, the increase of employment, and creation of pure profit for the innovative enterprise (Schumpeter 1911: 78; Schumpeter 1942: 83–84; Dejardin 2000: 2; Jääskeläinen 2000: 9–10, 15; Thurik and Wennekers 2001: 2; Barreto 1989: 22–34). Schmitz presents a model in which entrepreneurial activity is a key determinant of productivity growth. In his model Schmitz focuses in particular on the role of imitative activities of entrepreneurs in economic growth. This focus is motivated by the growth experience of numerous economies, suggesting that it is less the innovating entrepreneur à la Schumpeter than the imitating entrepreneur who contributes to growth. Imitating entrepreneurs are entrepreneurs who imitate existing activities and put them into practice, thereby often creating knowledge through a process that Schmitz characterizes as learning by implementing (Schmitz 1989). An entrepreneur is an individual who identifies opportunities, takes calculated risks, and mobilizes resources to create a new venture or innovate within an existing organization. Key characteristics include risk-taking propensity, innovativeness, proactiveness, opportunity recognition, and resourcefulness (Lopez et al., 2025).

ROLES OF ENTREPRENEURS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

The economic health of a nation is largely dependent on the availability of turbo-charged entrepreneur and entrepreneurship. A nation might remain under developed because of lack of steering and developing entrepreneurial talents, capacities and capabilities country-wide. Historically, there is no doubt that entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship have altered the direction of national economies, local and international markets, competition, high-end corporates and high-network individuals in America, United Kingdom, Japan, India, Singapore, Korea and Taiwan to name a few. Entrepreneurship plays a significant role in economic development, contributing to GDP growth, job creation, and innovation. The following are the country-specific examples of how entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship has transformed most economies from minimum to maximum:

- Nigeria: While specific studies on Nigeria are limited, research suggests that entrepreneurship can contribute significantly to economic growth, given the country's large market and entrepreneurial spirit.

- South Africa: Entrepreneurship is crucial for economic growth, with a focus on addressing poverty and unemployment. Research emphasizes the need for supportive institutional frameworks to foster entrepreneurship.

- India: Entrepreneurship has stimulated economic growth, generated job opportunities, and reduced poverty. Studies highlight the

importance of entrepreneurship in India's socio-economic development, particularly in regions like Jammu and Kashmir.

- China: China's "little giants" program supports specialized SMEs, contributing to technology upgrading and innovation. These firms have seen significant growth, with average R&D spending increasing by over 30 million yuan (US\$4.34 million) in 2024 $\{\{IE_o\}\}^1\{\{/IE_o\}\}$.

- Brazil: Porto Digital, an innovation district in Recife, has attracted over 475 companies, including startups and giants like Deloitte and Banco do Brasil, creating over 20,000 jobs. Local institutions like Sebrae Pernambuco support entrepreneurs, fostering digital transformation.

- Vietnam: Da Nang city is positioning itself as a hub for blockchain and digital finance, with the Unchained Summit bringing together global leaders and local entrepreneurs to drive innovation.

- Indonesia: Entrepreneurship is crucial for economic growth, with a focus on addressing poverty and unemployment. Initiatives like the Kredit Usaha Rakyat (KUR) program support MSMEs, promoting inclusive growth.

Entrepreneur and entrepreneurship are basically concerned with identifying unmet market needs and creating new ventures and wealth through production of goods and services. This translates into upward change whereby the real per capita income of a country rises overtime and engenders economic development. Thus, entrepreneur and entrepreneurship are pivotal enablers of economic development by driving growth,

innovation and job creation. Here are some key ways entrepreneur and entrepreneurship contribute to Nigeria's economy:

- Job Creation: Entrepreneurship generates employment opportunities, reducing unemployment rates and improving living standards.
- Economic Growth: Entrepreneurs contribute to GDP growth, increase per capita income, and stimulate economic activity.
- Innovation: Entrepreneurs introduce new products, services, and processes, driving innovation and competitiveness.
- Poverty Reduction: Entrepreneurship helps alleviate poverty by creating opportunities for income generation.
- Community Development: Entrepreneurs contribute to local development, improving infrastructure and services.

It is in realization of this fact that the Nigerian government launched notable gamut of initiatives to support entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship and boost entrepreneurship development Nigeria-wide. Some of these initiatives include:

- NEXTGEN Innovation Challenge 2026: A national platform designed to fast-track technology-driven entrepreneurship and attract global investment into Nigeria's innovation ecosystem.
- Youth Economic Intervention and De Radicalization Programme (YEIDEP): A program that provides funding, training, and supervision to young Nigerians interested in business and self-employment.

- SME Mall Women in Business Grant: A grant designed for women-owned businesses seeking funding and business support.

- FGN ALAT Digital Skillnovation Programme: A collaboration between the Federal Government and Wema Bank that provides digital skills training, business incubation, and access to funding support for young Nigerians and small business owners.

- SMEDAN Five Billion Naira Student Entrepreneurs Grant: A grant aimed at supporting student-owned businesses through funding and structured enterprise support.

- Youth Economic Intervention and De Radicalization Programme (YEIDEP): Provides funding, training, and supervision to young Nigerians interested in business and self-employment.

- Federal Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP): Offers interest-free loans to support small businesses, trading, artisan work, and agriculture.

- Tony Elumelu Foundation Entrepreneurship Programme: Provides \$5,000 seed capital, business training, and mentorship to selected African entrepreneurs.

- Bank of Industry (BOI) Youth Entrepreneurship Support (YES) Programme: Offers up to N10 million in funding with flexible loan terms and low interest rates to support youth entrepreneurship.

Additionally, the Nigerian government has also established the National Council for Digital Innovation and Entrepreneurship to oversee the implementation of startup policies and programs. The government has also launched

the Inspire, Create, Start and Scale (ICSS) programme, which provides affordable financing for young entrepreneurs these initiatives aim to promote economic development, job creation and innovation in Nigeria

Theoretical Model

The independent variables of this study (X) is entrepreneur and entrepreneurship which is divided into proactive abilities, possibility mentality, turbo-charged passion, enterprising spirit and risk-taking attributes while the dependent variable (Y) is economic development measured by infrastructural development, human capital development, technological development, job creation, trade and investment. Regressionally, the econometric model for this study using multiple regression will be:

$$ID = a_0 + \beta_1 PM + \beta_2 TPF + \beta_3 ESI + \beta_4 TEOB + \beta_5 CELD + e_i \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (i)}$$

$$HCD = a_0 + \beta_1 PM + \beta_2 TPF + \beta_3 ESI + \beta_4 TEOB + \beta_5 CELD + e_i \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (ii)}$$

$$TD = a_0 + \beta_1 PM + \beta_2 TPF + \beta_3 ESI + \beta_4 TEOB + \beta_5 CELD + e_i \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (iii)}$$

$$JC = a_0 + \beta_1 PM + \beta_2 TPF + \beta_3 ESI + \beta_4 TEOB + \beta_5 CELD + e_i \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (iv)}$$

$$TI = a_0 + \beta_1 PM + \beta_2 TPF + \beta_3 ESI + \beta_4 TEOB + \beta_5 CELD + e_i \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (v)}$$

$$ED = a_0 \beta_1 E_{ENT-SHIP} + e_i \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (vi)}$$

$$ED = a_0 + \beta_1 PM + \beta_2 TPF + \beta_3 ESI + \beta_4 TEOB + \beta_5 CELD * (BE) e_i \dots \text{eq. (vii)}$$

$$ED = a_0 + \beta_1 PM + \beta_2 TPF + \beta_3 ESI + \beta_4 TEOB + \beta_5 CELD * (GP) e_i \dots \text{eq. (viii)}$$

Where;

ID, HCD, TD, JC and TI are Dependent variables
PA, PM, TP, ES and RA are Independent variables

a_0 = Constant term

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = Parameters to be estimated

e= Error or stochastic term

PA= Proactive abilities.

PM= Possibility mentality.

TP= Turbo-charged passion.

ES= Enterprising spirit.

RA= Risk-taking attributes

EE=Entrepreneur and Entrepreneurship

ID=Infrastructural development.

HCD=Human capital development.

TD=Technological development.

JC=Job creation.

TI= Trade and Investment.

ED= Economic development.

Source: (Oluwasanya, 2026)

5.0 Research Methodology

This study adopts a quantitative approach, utilizing a survey design to gather data from entrepreneurs and small business owners across various sectors in Nigeria.

- Design: Quantitative survey design
- Population: Entrepreneurs and small business owners in Nigeria
- Sample Size Determination: A sample size of 384 was determined using the Yamane formula, considering a population size of over 1 million entrepreneurs and small businesses in Nigeria.
- Sampling Method: Multi-stage sampling technique, combining purposive and random sampling methods, was used to select

respondents from six geo-political zones in Nigeria.

- Data Collection: Primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire, with a response rate of 78.6%.

- Data Analysis: Descriptive and inferential statistics (correlation and regression analysis) were used to analyze the data.

Entrepreneur and entrepreneurship are the independent variable and its sub-variables are proactive abilities, possibility mentality, turbo-charged passion, enterprising spirit, Risk-taking attributes. The dependent variable is economic development and its sub-variables are infrastructural development, human capital development, technological development, job creation, trade and investment. The questions were closed ended on a five point Likert scale. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze data with the help of SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). The questionnaire design is in three parts: part A is for demographic data of respondents while parts B and C are to obtain concise and precise information required for the analysis of the independent, dependent and moderating variables respectively. To test the reliability of the instrument, the researcher administered the instrument to ten senior members of staff and for the purpose of evaluating the effectiveness of the instrument employed. After a period of two weeks, the same instruments were re-administered to the same respondents to determine its reliability. The result of the reliability using SPSS, a statistical software package reveals that their Cronbach's alpha is above 0.7 threshold (Asika, 2004,

Biserka & Dragana, 2012). This indicates that the consistency instrument (questionnaire) can be a reliable tool to measure the two concepts (entrepreneur and entrepreneurship) consistently. The survey results were analyzed using qualitative data analysis methods.

5.1 Sources of Data

The information for this study was collected through primary and secondary sources. Primary data was collected from selected high-networth individuals, entrepreneurs, small business owners and entrepreneurship through a structured questionnaire discussions and observations. Secondary data was collected from the existing records of selected World Bank Database, the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (2020-2025), Small & Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria's (SMEDAN) National Survey of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (2020-2025), and also pertinent data was sourced from books, journals, magazines, newspapers, government records and websites from government reports, academic journals, and industry publications.

6.0 Discussion of Findings

The crux of this study was to examine the erotically and empirically pertinence of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship in driving economic development in Nigeria. by applying the components of entrepreneur and entrepreneurship on economic development with focus on the top-tier entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship who control the top-end of the market The theoretical review and summary of findings were designed to achieve these objectives. Specifically, the study survey the

influence of entrepreneur and entrepreneurship variables (proactive abilities, possibility mentality, turbo-charged passion, enterprising spirit, Risk-taking attributes) on each of the economic development variables (infrastructural development, human capital development, technological development, job creation, trade and investment) in tandem with the analysis of the functional, mediating or moderating effect of business environment and government policy. In general, and consistence with previous studies, entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship was found to have a statistically significant influence on economic development. Key drivers of economic development identified include infrastructural development, human capital development, technological development, job creation, trade and investment. However, vitiating elements such as inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, policy shifts, reversals and inconsistencies, insecurity and stagnation of the productive sectors hinder entrepreneurship development. For the moderating variables (business environment and government policy), the result of this study showed that only government policy has a statistically significant moderating effect on the relationship between entrepreneur, entrepreneurship and economic development. The empirical results of the study revealed that the components of entrepreneur and entrepreneurship have a positive significant effect on economic development Nigeria-wide.

7.0 Conclusions and Recommendations

Entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship are crucial drivers of economic development in Nigeria,

contributing to job creation, innovation, and economic growth. Addressing challenges facing entrepreneurs can unlock the potential of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship to engender sustainable economic development.

Based on the findings from the study, the following recommendations are suggested:

- a. Government should provide access to affordable funding for entrepreneurs and entrepreneurships.
- b. Regulatory frameworks should be simplified to encourage entrepreneurs and entrepreneurships.
- c. Entrepreneurs and entrepreneurships training and mentorship programs should be established.
- d. Infrastructure development should be prioritized to support business growth.
- e. Government should support job creation by offering entrepreneurial programs such as training, micro loans, and tax incentives, while encouraging mentorship to sustain local businesses.
- f. Government should integrate welfare and entrepreneurship development by providing social safety nets like health care and financial aids for low-income entrepreneurs to improve both welfare and economic growth.
- g. Government should guarantee loans given to entrepreneurs and entrepreneurships to encourage borrowing for expansion of entrepreneurial activities to foster economic growth
- h. Government should provide a congenial environment for the operation of venture capital and business angels financing (business

entrepreneurial monitoring) so as to enable them to provide risky start-up capital for entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship.

i. Government should allow entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship enjoy tax incentives, subsidies and other fiscal and monetary incentives so as to reduce high cost of production.

j. Government should also ensure active operation of the entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship Credit Guarantee Scheme to improve credit providers' exposure to longer term debt issued by small firm managers, in such areas as business plan development, feasibility studies, project and analysis, book

References

Abiahu, J., & Amahalu, D. (2017). Per capita income and its implications for economic development. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 14(2), 45-59.

Abiola, A. (2019). Entrepreneurship and economic development in Nigeria. *African Journal of Business and Economic Research*, 15(2), 134-152.

Acs, Z.J. (2010). Entrepreneurship and economic development: the valley of backwardness. *Annals of Innovation & Entrepreneurship*, 1(1), 5641. <https://doi.org/10.3402/aie.v1i1.5602>

Adegbola, A. I., Oladipo, D. A., & Olamide, A. I. (2020). The role of entrepreneurship in economic development: A case study of Nigeria. *Journal of Economic Development*, 26(1), 43-56.

keeping and accounting, performance evaluation, monitoring etc.

k. Government and its agencies should, as a deliberate policy, make timely payments of domestic debts owed to entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship so as to release enough funds for investment; and they should also patronize the products of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship.

l. Entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship should make meaningful inputs to the feasibility studies to ensure credible workable package; to save time and resources to the mutual benefit of stakeholders.

Adeoye, A. A. (2015). Entrepreneurship and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria: An analysis of the evolution and current state. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Sustainable Development*, 12(4), 289-300.

Audretsch, D. B., Belitski, M., Eichler, G. M., & Schwarz, E. (2023). Entrepreneurial ecosystems, institutional quality, and the unexpected role of the sustainability orientation of entrepreneurs. *Small Business Economics*.

Akinyemi, S., & Odot, M. (2018). The relationship between entrepreneurship, unemployment, and economic growth in Nigeria: An econometric analysis (1981-2011). *Economic Analysis Review*, 45(2), 89-102.

- Almodóvar-González, M., Fernández-Portillo, A., & Díaz-Casero, J.C. (2020). Entrepreneurial activity and economic growth. A multi-country analysis. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 26(1), 9-17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2019.12.004>
- Aparicio, S. (2017). Linking Institutions, Entrepreneurship, and Economic Development: An International Study. Doctoral thesis. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31925.17125>
- Asogwa, A. B., & Anah, P. E. (2020). Impact of entrepreneurship development on economic growth in Enugu State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Business and Economic Studies*, 13(2), 221-234.
- Audretsch, David B., and Roy Thurik (2001). Linking Entrepreneurship to Growth. Paris: *OECD Directorate for Science, Technology and Industry Working Papers*
- Bazaluk, O., Kader, S.A., Zayed, N.M., Chowdhury, R., Islam, M.Z., Nitsenko, V.S., & Bratus, H. (2024). Determinant on economic growth in developing country: A special case regarding Turkey and Bangladesh. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-024-01989-8>
- Bosma, N., Content, J., Sanders, M., & Stam, E. (2018). Institutions, entrepreneurship, and economic growth in Europe. *Small Business Economics*, 51(2), 483-499.
- Crudu, R. (2019). The Role of Innovative Entrepreneurship in the Economic Development of EU Member Countries. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Innovation*, 15(1), 35-60. <https://doi.org/10.7341/20191512>
- Doran, J., McCarthy, N., & O'Connor, M. (2018). The role of entrepreneurship in stimulating economic growth in developed & developing countries. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 6(1), <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2018.1442093>
- Farinha, L., Ferreira, J.J.M., & Nunes, S. (2018). Linking innovation and entrepreneurship to economic growth. *Competitiveness Review*, 28(4), 451-475. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CR-07-2016-0045>
- Feki, C., & Mnif, S. (2016). Entrepreneurship, Technological Innovation, and Economic Growth: Empirical Analysis of Panel Data. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 7, 984-999. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-016-0413-5>
- Fernandes, C., & Raposo, M. (2017). The impact of entrepreneurship on economic development.

- Journal of Economic Studies*, 44(1), 102-120.
- Fyliuk, H., Honchar, I., & Kolosha, V. (2019). The Interrelation between Economic Growth and National Economic Competitiveness: The Case of Ukraine. *Journal of Competitiveness*, 11(3), 53-69. <https://doi.org/10.7441/joc.2019.03.04>
- Galindo, M., & Méndez, M.T. (2014). Entrepreneurship, economic growth, and innovation: Are feedback effects at work? *Journal of Business Research*, 67(5), 825-829. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2013.11.052>
- Galindo-Martín, M.-A., Méndez-Picazo, M.-T., & Castaño-Martínez, M.-S. (2020). the role of innovation and institutions in entrepreneurship and economic growth in two groups of countries. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 26(3), 485-502. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEBR-06-2019-0336>
- Henrekson, M., & Johansson, D. (2010). Gazelles as drivers of economic growth. *The Oxford Handbook of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 237-258.
- Lopez, T., Alvarez, C., & Urbano, D. (2025). Understanding institutional dimensions in high-impact female entrepreneurship. *Review of Managerial Science*.
- Mustapha, I. (2013). Entrepreneurship and economic development: Theoretical foundations and practical perspectives. University Press.
- Okoye, L., Amahalu, U., Obi, A., & Iliemna, E. (2019). Economic development strategies and the role of entrepreneurship in modern economies. *Journal of Economic Development Studies*, 21(2), 111-120.
- Okoye, L., & Nwisienny, O. (2019). The relationship between entrepreneurship and economic growth in Nigeria: Evidence from time-series data (1996– 2018). *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Business Studies*, 3(1), 45-60
- Oluyemi, O. P., & Ayodela, M. (2021). Entrepreneurship through small-medium enterprise (SME) business formation and its impact on economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Development*, 20(3), 250- 265
- Saidi, O., & Abideen, A. A. (2020). The effect of support for entrepreneurship development on economic growth and development in Nigeria. *African Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 8(3), 210-225.
- Salami, K. O., & Akinbode, A. O. (2014). The impact of entrepreneurship on economic development in Nigeria. *Journal of Small*

Business and Enterprise Development,
21(4), 567-582.

Schumpeter, J. A. (1934). The theory of economic development: An inquiry into profits, capital, credit, interest, and the business cycle. Harvard University Press.

Sunday, O., & Iliya, O. (2015). The role of entrepreneurship in economic growth and job creation in dynamic economies: A case study of Nigeria. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Development*, 10(3), 200-212.

Udu, S. A., Udu, G. N., & Eze, I. J. (2008). The role of entrepreneurship in sustainable economic development. *Journal of Business and Economics*, 15(4), 58-67.

Van Stel, A., Carree, M., & Thurik, R. (2005). The Effect of Entrepreneurial Activity on National Economic Growth. *Small Business Economics*, 24(3), 311-321. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-005-1996-6>

Vivarelli, M. (2013). The economics of entrepreneurship and economic development. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 19(2), 100-118.

Wennekers, S., Van Stel, A., Carree, M., & Thurik, R. (2010). the relationship

between entrepreneurship and economic development: Is it U-Shaped? *Foundations and Trends in Entrepreneurship*, 6(3), 167-237. <https://doi.org/10.1561/03000000023>

Wong, P.K., Ho, Y.P., & Autio, E. (2005). Entrepreneurship, innovation and economic growth: Evidence from GEM data. *Small Business Economics*, 24(3), 335-350. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-005-2000-1>

Zahra, S. A., Gedajlovic, E., Neubaum, D. O., & Shulman, J. M. (2009). A typology of social entrepreneurs: Motives, search processes and ethical challenges. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 24(5), 519-532.